

Organization's Ethics, Job Performance Satisfaction and Effects on Employees' Engagement and Commitment

Authors : Anunya Thanasrisuebwong

Abstract : This research paper aimed to find out how was the ethical climate in an organization and job performance satisfaction of employees affected employees' engagement and commitment by using the case study of PTT Exploration and Production Public Company Limited, Thailand. The population of this research was 4,383 Thai employees of PTTEP, Thailand. From a total of 420 questionnaires sent out, 345 respondents replied. The statistics utilized was mean score and Multiple Regression Analysis. The findings revealed that the respondents had opinion towards ethical climate of their organization, job performance satisfaction and organization engagement and commitment at a high level. The test of hypothesis disclosed the determinant attributes of job performance satisfaction that affected the respondents' overall level of organization engagement and commitment. The set of these determinant attributes consisted of employees' responsibilities for duties, organization's policies and practice, relationship with organization's commanders, work security and stability, job description, career path and relationship with colleagues. These variables were able to predict the employees' organization engagement and commitment at 50.6 percent.

Keywords : ethical climate in organization, job performance satisfaction, organization engagement, commitment

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